

USE OF OPTICAL FIBER SENSORS IN AUTOCLAVE MOLDING OF GFRP LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: A real-time measurement of internal and residual strains in GFRP laminates with an optical fiber strain sensor is performed in an autoclave molding. An Extrinsic Fabry-Perot Interferometric (EFPI) type optical fiber strain sensor is embedded into prepreg sheets before the molding. The ion viscosity and the temperature of the epoxy resin matrix are also simultaneously measured with the internal strain measurement. The results of the experiments shows that the internal and the residual strain of GFRP laminates during the molding can be monitored by the optical fiber sensor. It is also found that the circumstances around the embedded optical fiber strain sensor should be taken into account for the interpretation of the measured internal and residual strain.

KEYWORDS: internal strain, residual strain, autoclave molding, optical fiber strain sensor, cure process, GFRP laminate, ion viscosity

INTRODUCTION

Advanced composite materials are usually cured by autoclaves. Mechanical properties of molded products strongly depends on the molding conditions. The cure conditions such as temperature, pressure and their timings and rates etc. in the autoclave molding are empirically determined by some trial-and-error tests. Such process might be time consuming if products have varieties of e.g., their shape and thickness, of matrix materials and reinforcing fibers. Therefore it is strongly desired to establish a way of determining an optimum cure condition which can be automatically adapted to varieties of moldings. For this purpose, the optimum cure condition has to be determined based on the data of the degree of matrix cure, void content and residual stress and/or strain etc. within products manufactured under various molding conditions. Among them, the degree of matrix cure is most important, and residual stress data are also needed for they considerably affect the mechanical properties of products. Real-time monitoring during the molding is expected to be the best way to obtain their data. Recently studies of real-time monitoring of matrix cure with optical fiber sensors have been performed. Druy et al. have reported a cure monitoring with infrared-transmitting optical fiber sensors[1]. An ultrasonic detection technique with optical fibers has been applied to a cure monitoring by Ohn et al.[2]. Myrick et al. have reported a cure monitoring using Raman

spectrum measurement with optical fibers[3]. Their works have shown that the real-time cure monitoring at any position in the laminates is possible using optical fiber sensors which have the same shape as reinforcing fibers. Wang et al. determined residual stresses by curled shape of unsymmetric laminates after molding[4]. Analysis of residual stresses due to cool-down from the post cure for the symmetric cross-ply composites has been performed by Chen et al., but the experiment has not yet been done[5]. A paper on real-time monitoring of residual stresses and/or strains has not been found until now.

In the present study, a real-time monitoring method of internal strains is investigated with embedded optical strain sensors in GFRP laminates during autoclave molding process. In the experiment, ion viscosity and temperature of the epoxy resin matrix are simultaneously measured with the internal strains. Comparing their results, the relationship between internal strains and the cure process is investigated.

OPTICAL FIBER STRAIN SENSOR

In the measurement of internal strains, Fiber Optic Strain Gage System II (FOSS II) (Fiber & Sensor Technologies) was used. It had an optical fiber sensor whose sensing type was an Extrinsic Fabry-Perot Interferometric (EFPI) one. A schematic diagram of the EFPI strain sensor is shown in figure 1. FOSS II detects small changes of the length of air gap and converts them to strains using a gage factor of each strain sensor. The strain is measured by the following process. FOSS II transmits laser beam into the input/output optical fiber, and detects the intensity of the beam reflected by the reflector in the sensor. The operating temperature and resolution of the EFPI strain sensor in this experiment are -272 to $+350$ °C and $10,000$ $\mu\epsilon$ in the full scale. The gage size of the EFPI strain sensor was 350 $\mu\text{m} \times 4$ mm.

Fig.1 Schematic diagram of the EFPI strain sensor

DIELECTRIC CONSTANT MONITORING

The electric property of thermoset resins is in general dielectric from its liquid to solid phases. The dielectric response under AC field is the sum of contributions from dipole moments and

ionic charges. Development of the gelation and polymerization reduces the mobilities of dipoles and isolated ions. Therefore dielectric response can be an indicator of solidification of high-polymers, in particular the loss part of dielectric constant is convenient to estimate the solidification.

Let the complex specific dielectric constant be ϵ under AC electric field. ϵ is written as, by definition,

$$\epsilon = \epsilon' - i\epsilon'' \quad (1)$$

where ϵ' , and ϵ'' are the specific dielectric constant and the loss factor respectively. The latter is closely related to the solidification process of polymers. The loss factor ϵ'' can be expressed as

$$\epsilon'' = \frac{\sigma}{\omega\epsilon_0} + \frac{(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_h)\omega\tau}{1 + \omega^2\tau^2} \quad (2)$$

where

- σ = ionic conductivity,
- ω = angular frequency of the applied AC field,
- ϵ_0 = permeability of the vacuum,
- ϵ_l = relaxed permeability,
- ϵ_h = unrelaxed permeability,
- τ = relaxation time.

When the frequency is not very high ($\omega\tau \ll 1$), the loss factor is reduced to the ionic contribution only, i.e.,

$$\epsilon'' = \frac{\sigma}{\omega\epsilon_0} \quad (3)$$

Therefore the conductivity measurement gives the loss factor in the low frequency approximation. The reciprocal of conductivity $1/\sigma$ i.e., the electric resistance, is particularly convenient to estimate the solidification since its minimum (maximum) corresponds to the maximum (minimum) mobility of ions in polymers. The resistance $1/\sigma$ is also called the ion viscosity since it has a clear correspondence with the usual viscosity measured by a rheometer. The ion viscosity measurement by dielectric monitoring is more convenient than usual viscosity because the ion viscosity can be continuously measured through all phases of polymers. On the other hand, the rheometer can only measure the liquid viscosity [6].

EXPERIMENT

In the autoclave molding experiment, GFRP laminates were used. The prepreg used was GF Scotch-ply 1009-36 by 3M and the matrix resin was high temperature type epoxy. Their stacking configurations were $[0_8]$ and $[0_2/90_2/0_2]$. Different cure patterns corresponding to their stacking configurations were adopted. Two EFPI strain sensors were embedded in the middle plane of the laminates in stacking process of prepreps. Location of two EFPI strain sensors embedded within composite layers is shown in Figure 2. The dielectric sensor was also set up within prepreps in stacking process. A schematic diagram of monitoring system in the experiment is shown in figure 3. The signal cables of EFPI strain sensors (effectively optical fibers) and a dielectric sensor were connected to measurement apparatus out of the

autoclave. The way of pulling the cables out of the autoclave were devised in order to keep sealing up it. The strain responses of GFRP laminates from the EFPI strain sensor were measured by the FOSS II system, being saved in a personal computer by an AD converter. The dielectric responses and temperature of resin were measured by Eumetric 100A of Micromet Instruments, being saved in a personal computer by a RS232C interface.

Fig.2 Location of EFPI strain sensors within a UD laminate

Fig.3 Schematic diagram of monitoring system

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Unidirectional Laminate

The curing pattern in the autoclave molding for unidirectional laminate is shown in figure 4. Figure 5 shows the measured results of change in ion viscosity of epoxy matrix and temperature of the material. The magnitude of change in the ion viscosity is indicated by $\log(1/\sigma)$. The abscissa of the figure shows the molding time. The ion viscosity rapidly decreases at the first temperature increasing stage. This corresponds to melting of the epoxy matrix. From this change of the ion viscosity, it is found that all matrix have finished to melt at about 50 min of the molding time. Then the ion viscosity slightly changes at the constant temperature stage. At the post cure stage, it gradually approaches to a definite value, namely, the cure is almost completed. At the last cooling stage, the ion viscosity rapidly increases.

Fig.4 Curing pattern in autoclave molding

Fig.5 Change in ion viscosity and temperature

Figure 6 shows the experimental results of internal strains by two EFPI strain sensors. In the figure, A is the strain obtained by the EFPI strain sensor embedded in the same direction with the reinforcing fiber of unidirectional laminates. B shows the strain obtained by the strain sensor embedded perpendicularly to the fiber direction. The strain A gradually increases at the first temperature increasing stage. It shows the maximum value before the ion viscosity shows the minimum. And then it begins to gradually decrease. It changes from the tensile strain to the compressive one and it increases until the molding is completed. In the same way as the result of A, B rapidly increases at the first temperature increasing stage and shows the maximum value before the ion viscosity denotes the minimum. It changes from the tensile to the compressive and shows the maximum compressive value at the second temperature increasing stage. In the same way as the change of the ion viscosity, it gradually approaches to a definite value. At the last cooling stage, it rapidly increases.

Fig.6 Internal strain responses of GFRP UD laminate

Crossply Laminates

Figure 7 shows the cure pattern in the autoclave molding for crossply laminates. In the figure, two kinds of molding conditions with different cooling rates at the last molding stage are shown. One is the rate of 4.6°C/min and another is that of 2.3°C/min.

Figure 8 shows the measured results of change in the ion viscosity of epoxy matrix and temperature within the autoclave. They show the same change as those of the unidirectional laminate do with the change of temperature and pressure in the autoclave molding. The ion viscosity increases abruptly at the molding time of about 140 min., when the gelation of the epoxy matrix begins.

Figure 9 shows the internal strains measured by the EFPI strain sensors embedded in the same direction with the reinforcing fibers in central laminae of the crossply laminate. In the figure CL1 represents the result of the laminate molded with the cooling rate of 4.6°C/min and CL2 represents that of 2.3°C/min. In spite of the same molding conditions except for the last cooling rates, the strain responses of CL1 and CL2 show the very different change till 200 min of the molding time. After 200 min, the strain of CL1 keeps the same value till 270 min

when the cooling stage begins and then it decreases. In the cooling stage, it changes uniformly and to the compressive strain. CL2 shows the same tendency to change.

Figure 10 shows the internal strains measured by the EFPI strain sensors embedded in the perpendicular direction to the reinforcing fibers in central laminae of the crossply laminate. In the figure CT1 represents the result of the laminate molded with the cooling rate of 4.6°C/min and CT2 represents that of 2.3°C/min. The strain responses of CT1 and CT2 show the very different change till 200 min. After 200 min, they are constant till 270 min at the beginning of the cooling stage. This tendency of change is the same in CL1 and CL2. After 270 min, their strains increase uniformly.

Fig.7 Curing pattern in autoclave molding

Fig.8 Change in ion viscosity and temperature

Fig.9 Strain responses of CL1 and CL2

Fig.10 Strain responses of CT1 and CT2

The residual strain of the laminate in which the EFPI strain sensor was embedded in the same direction with the reinforcing fibers is the compressive one. On the other hand, the residual strain of the laminate in which the EFPI strain sensor was embedded in the perpendicular direction to the reinforcing fibers is tensile. The compressive residual strain is generally expected to develop in the laminate by the shrinkage of the epoxy matrix at the cooling stage in the molding. But the contradictory result was obtained in the measurement of the residual strain in the laminate which contained the strain sensors embedded in the perpendicular direction to the reinforcing fibers. The reason why the tensile residual strains took place is investigated below.

As the EFPI strain sensor is very large in comparison with the reinforcing glass fibers, the strain measured by the sensor can be different from that of the reinforcing fibers. Therefore the state of the embedded strain sensor within the laminate can influence the result measured by it. In order to examine, the micrographs of the state of the embedded strain sensor were

taken. Figures 11 and 12 are the micrographs of the cross-section of the part in which the strain sensors were embedded in the perpendicular direction to the reinforcing fibers. Figure 11 shows the cross-section which was made by cutting along the same direction with the EFPI strain sensor. Figure 12 shows the cross-section which was made by the cutting along the perpendicular direction to the EFPI strain sensor. The diameter of the sensing part of the EFPI strain sensor is very large in comparison with the reinforcing fibers. The embedding the strain sensor into the laminate gives rise to the resin rich region neighboring to the sensor. From this figure, it is known that the sensing part of the sensor is loaded with the transverse compression. In the case of the sensor embedded in the same direction with the reinforcing fibers, the resin rich region was not found. It is thought that the different result of the residual strain is due to such different surrounding conditions of the sensor. However this explanation is not yet confirmed, so it is necessary to be validated.

Fig.11 Micrograph of the EFPI strain sensor embedded in the crossply laminate (the cross-section perpendicular to the sensor)

Fig.12 Micrograph of the EFPI strain sensor embedded in the crossply laminate (the cross-section along the sensor)

CONCLUSION

In this paper, the applicability of optical fiber sensors to real-time measurement of internal and residual strains in GFRP laminates was investigated in an autoclave molding. In the measurement an EFPI strain sensor was used. The results of experiments showed that the internal strain of GFRP laminates during the molding can be monitored by the EFPI strain sensor and the residual strains of the laminates can be estimated from the internal strains measured at the end of the molding. But it was found that the measured data by the EFPI strain sensor do not directly indicate the internal strain of the reinforcing fibers or matrix resins. Therefore it was recognized that the measured strain data by the EFPI strain sensor should be converted to the true internal strain taking account of the embedded circumstances of the sensor in the laminates.

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